

ELECTRONIC LEARNING SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES OF THEIR CREATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7997109>

Annotation: This article contains opinions and news about electronic education systems and their creation technologies. A new generation of students, global competition in the field of higher education, the development of e-learning - all this leads to a change in the education paradigm, to a new understanding of how people should and can learn.

Key words: Higher education, Non-formal education, learning platforms, teaching methodology,

The current agenda for the university includes answers to the following questions: how can the university help students learn more effectively? How to ensure the competencies that are in demand in the labor market? How to help students gain practical experience in solving professional problems? New learning models are aimed at identifying the abilities of students and teaching them how to use them, rather than filling them with knowledge like a vessel with water. It is necessary not only to form skills, but also to understand why and how people learn, surrounded by various exciting gadgets. Those. the main thing today is to interest and motivate the student to study, to learn new things,

Non-formal education, which people receive outside of institutional structures, using open educational resources and online learning platforms, is becoming more and more in demand. This leads to a new understanding of the role of university education and includes the following expectations:

- competition and the development of technologies will contribute to the fact that through the use of open educational resources, mass professional education will become more accessible;
- education can be received not at universities, but in professional communities, including virtual ones;
- the paradigm of how people should learn will change;
- education should not be fixated only on tests or tests;
- instead of competition in the new paradigm of education, there should be a very high degree of cooperation;
- learning should be built around the student with the strengthening of the role of feedback from the teacher;
- subjectivity in the perception of educational material by students should be encouraged;
- more and more educational innovations are associated with edutainment - the use of gaming (entertainment) technologies in the educational process.

The key point for understanding the consequences of the transition to e-learning is the organization of learning - the classroom is reduced, the individual workload increases, the

student works more independently, in an electronic environment, interacting with other students with the participation of a teacher. Other effects of the transition to e-learning:

- it becomes possible to organize the process of systematic testing of learning - the increment of knowledge (skills);
- more efficient management (updating, publication) of educational resources is provided, their availability is improved, reuse is guaranteed;
- the dependence of the student on the teacher decreases and the psychological burden on students and teachers in the process of mutual communication decreases;
- develop individual abilities, independence, initiative and responsibility of students;
- a transition is being made from an explanatory-illustrative and reproductive teaching methodology to a reflexive model, which involves strengthening the independent work of students, creativity, revealing individual characteristics while maintaining opportunities for communication with other students and the teacher.

University teachers actively use modern educational technologies in the educational process. This helps to improve the quality of education and the effectiveness of the educational process, create additional competitive advantages in the context of the development of the Internet, the emergence of a new lifestyle and the emergence of a generation of “digital natives” who, from a young age, encounter computers and want to learn “in a new way”, use them in their studies. smartphones, tablets, laptops and Internet resources, play an active role in the educational process and future professional activities.

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